

Growing Up in the Online World

DSIT Consultation Response

Dr Cristina Costa and Dr Michaela Oliver, Durham University
Digital Literacies Network: <https://digitalliteraciesnetwork.com/>

This submission responds to the UK Government's consultation on children's and young people's online experiences. It draws on evidence from co-produced research on youth digital engagement in North East England (a full summary of co-production insights with young people is provided in Appendix 1), as well as findings from our projects on [Digital Wellbeing](#), and [Digital Masculinity](#), and a broader body of research on young people's interactions with digital technologies.

Key position

Blanket social media bans risk reducing what is fundamentally a systemic, technological, and commercial issue to a young people's problem, thereby individualising the problem as if it were inherently caused by youth behaviour.

We argue that the issue is multifaceted and complex and cannot be addressed by focusing on a single factor or actor alone. Many harms are embedded in platform design, including algorithmically driven interaction, weak moderation, and commercially incentivised architectures. Effective policy should therefore recognise shared responsibility across governments, technology companies, families, and users, while addressing the economic models that shape digital environments and strengthening access to digital literacy development: training for professionals and learning for young people and parents.

At the same time, digital wellbeing requires a broader conceptualisation. Rather than focusing narrowly on individual use of digital technologies or their screen time, i.e., a human-computer interaction, it is key that policy also recognises young people's online lives as social and relational, shaping identity, belonging, learning, creativity, and civic participation within complex digital ecosystems. Accounting for the quality of digital engagement is key to developing a more comprehensive understanding of digital safety and wellbeing.

Responsibility and accountability

Public debate often frames online harm as a consequence of children's behaviour. This is misleading. Evidence from research with young people shows that when trusted, supported, and given critical know-how, they are capable of acting ethically and safely online, regardless of age (Costa and Oliver, 2023; 2025a; 2025b).

At the same time, young people need space to learn through experience, including making mistakes. Such opportunities are essential for developing resilience and

judgement. However, these learning processes should not occur in environments that exploit errors through platform design or malicious actors. Safeguarding must therefore protect against exploitation without removing opportunities for development.

A comprehensive approach to accountability must include:

- **Technology companies:** Stronger regulation is needed, alongside clearly defined duties of care. Where harm is evident, responses should extend beyond financial penalties to enforceable design standards and, where necessary, restrictions on market access. Current platform architectures prioritise profit and high levels of user activity over wellbeing and safety.
- **Government:** Government must establish robust regulatory frameworks and exercise meaningful oversight of platform design and algorithmic systems in coordination with the countries in which these platforms are based. National regulation alone is insufficient; coordinated international pressure, particularly involving jurisdictions where major companies are based, such as the United States, is needed to ensure the effective enforcement of standards and sanctions (Srivastava, 2026; Wynn-Williams, 2025).
- **Parents and other responsible adults:** Digital literacy varies widely across adults and households, shaped by factors such as occupation, education, socioeconomic and cultural background, and geographic and place-based differences. Engagement with digital environments is influenced not only by age but also by cultural expectations and professional demands, leaving many people to navigate unfamiliar systems. Parents benefit from support through trusted and inclusive education and awareness initiatives, enabling them to build confidence and offer informed guidance, rather than being expected to provide unrealistic or uninformed levels of oversight.
- **Children and young people:** Young people should be recognised as rights holders with agency, not as the primary source of harm. Empowerment requires equipping them with critical digital literacies while acknowledging structural constraints on their choices (Costa and Oliver, 2025a).
- **Law, regulation, and enforcement:** Legal approaches must move from reactive responses to preventative frameworks. This requires updating legal definitions of digital abuse so they accurately reflect contemporary forms of harm, including algorithmic amplification, coordinated harassment, and exploitative engagement practices. Regulation must go beyond addressing individual incidents to confront the systemic, design-driven harms embedded within platform infrastructures themselves.

At the same time, there is an urgent need to strengthen international legal coordination. Existing frameworks are struggling to keep pace with digital safety challenges, as the rapid development of technologies such as AI and borderless social platforms outpaces the slow, consensus-driven nature of global treaty processes. Ongoing disagreements between states over fundamental principles,

including the balance between freedom of expression, national security, and user privacy, further fragment the regulatory landscape. Without meaningful reform, international law will remain ill-equipped to address the scale and complexity of digital harms.

Limitations of blanket social media bans

Enforcement challenges

Evidence shows that enforcing youth social media bans is extremely difficult. Adolescents frequently circumvent restrictions by falsifying age, using shared accounts, employing VPNs, or exploiting weaknesses in verification systems (Internet Matters, 2026; Ofcom, 2024). Findings from Australia's under-16 social media ban indicate low compliance: only about a quarter of 14–15-year-olds fully complied within four months (Bursztyn, 2026). Young people widely perceive non-compliance among peers, reinforcing continued usage. These dynamics reflect the networked nature of social media, where behaviour is shaped by peer norms and a sense of belonging. Similar patterns have been observed in highly regulated contexts such as China, highlighting the persistent difficulty of enforcement even under strict regimes (Mou, 2016; Xiao, 2020).

Emerging evidence indicates that social media bans are beginning to generate unintended and potentially adverse outcomes, including reducing young people's exposure to news and current affairs (Notley et al., 2026), with possible negative implications for their civic awareness and participation.

This development presents a policy paradox. While existing measures often seek to safeguard young people, they may simultaneously undermine broader policy objectives aimed at fostering informed, critically engaged, and active citizens.

Structural limitations

Bans target access rather than underlying harms. Issues such as algorithmically driven interaction, harmful content amplification, weak moderation, and exploitative design features affect users of all ages.

Social consequences

Blanket social media bans:

- Lack sensitivity to context, disproportionately affecting marginalised groups, including LGBTQ+ young people, those in rural areas, or those reliant on online communities for support.
- Risk increasing social exclusion, particularly where peer groups span mixed ages.
- Ignore the positive aspects of online engagement, including learning, creativity, civic participation, and peer support.
- Create inconsistencies across platforms (e.g. social features in gaming or educational tools often remain unregulated).

- Assume sudden competence at a fixed age threshold, without providing developmental support or digital education.

Rethinking digital wellbeing

Research shows that adolescent behaviour is strongly shaped by peer influence and perceived norms (Irani et al., 2024). Adolescents exhibit heightened sensitivity to peer feedback and expectations, often aligning their behaviour with that of their social group to maintain a sense of belonging and status (Laursen and Veenstra, 2021). Social media intensifies these dynamics by making peer activity continuously visible and reinforcing normative pressures at scale (Ceilutka, 2023). As a result, even well-designed regulatory interventions may struggle to gain traction unless a critical mass of users disengages simultaneously.

Conventional approaches to digital wellbeing emphasise individual self-regulation. The research we have been conducting at Durham University proposes a complementary perspective based on intersubjective recognition (Costa, 2026). Digital environments are social spaces where recognition - visibility, acknowledgement, and validation - is unevenly distributed and often mediated through shallow metrics such as likes and follower counts. These systems reinforce power imbalances and incentivise performative behaviour.

Young people, often seeking a sense of belonging and meaningful connection, instead encounter environments structured around visibility, popularity, and monetisation. Influencer economies further complicate this landscape, with economic incentives sometimes encouraging ethically questionable practices.

From this perspective, online environments are regarded as social spaces where intersubjective recognition – so essential to one’s social existence and even more so online, where tangible forms of acknowledgement are necessary to note one’s presence - is unevenly distributed and often mediated by shallow metrics such as likes, shares, and follower counts. These forms of quantifiable validation are embedded in platform designs that amplify asymmetric power relations (uneven relationships, i.e., following someone without being followed, thus exposing themselves to a wider network of unknown people) and incentivise performative engagement.

Such systems are particularly harmful to young people, who often seek meaningful connection and a sense of belonging in digital networks. Instead, they encounter environments where visibility, popularity, and monetisation shape interaction, their experience and their views of themselves via these spaces. Digital content creators, also known as digital influencers, operating within these ecosystems may engage in ethically questionable practices driven by economic incentives, often with limited accountability (see Theroux, 2026) at the pretence of freedom of expression.

Digital environments require a stronger emphasis on shared responsibility and ethical participation. As explored in our work on digital wellbeing, online networks should

operate according to a shared code of conduct grounded in mutual care, accountability, and recognition. From this point of view, every user is not only responsible for their own wellbeing but for that of other users; they are both participants and co-creators of healthier digital spaces (see Costa, 2026).

This shift has direct implications for platform design. Moving away from extractive, engagement-driven architectures toward systems that support meaningful interaction, reciprocity, and community accountability (Costa et al., 2024) is essential for fostering sustainable digital wellbeing.

A transformational approach is needed towards environments grounded in mutual care, accountability, and ethical participation to create a model in which users are both beneficiaries and co-creators of healthier digital spaces.

Mental health and commercial design

Online harms are inseparable from platform business models (Costa, 2026; forthcoming). Key concerns include:

- Algorithmic amplification optimised for engagement rather than wellbeing
- Exposure to unrealistic lifestyles and influencer cultures
- Normalisation of harmful behaviour
- Suppression of counter-narratives

These harms are often less visible than physical risks but require urgent regulatory attention. Age-based access restrictions alone do not address these underlying issues.

Educating society

Effective responses must extend beyond children:

- Parents and carers need support to navigate digital environments
- Public understanding of platform power and influence must be strengthened
- Digital harms should be recognised as structural and technical issues, not merely behavioural ones

Why social media is so important for young people

Our ongoing research with young people shows that social media can play a significant role in young people's lives, enabling:

- Maintenance of friendships and social connections
- Participation in interest-based and mixed-age communities
- Exposure to diverse perspectives
- Informal learning and skills development
- Civic engagement and political awareness
- Exploration of identity in low-risk settings
- Support networks for marginalised groups

For some, these platforms compensate for limited offline opportunities, including reduced youth services and restricted access to physical social spaces. Policy responses must reflect this complex reality.

Creation of digital codes of practice

Rather than relying on exclusionary approaches, young people should be supported through digital codes of conduct that they can help create, which aim to recognise them as ethical digital users. We have evidence that this is a more effective way to work with young people (see Costa and Oliver, 2023, 2025a).

These codes should be grounded in key principles such as rights, respect, honesty, accountability, care for others, and responsible sharing. Such an approach frames wellbeing not only in terms of human-computer interaction, but also through the lens of interpersonal subjectivity. It emphasises how each digital user, as an active participant in social exchange, both gives and receives recognition, an essential process for social validation and the affirmation of shared humanity.

Human Computer interaction arguments		Intersubjective recognition	
Instrumental perspective Technical solutions	Interfaces / design	Care (social belonging) – being acknowledged as a key member of the community	Relational perspective focused on the quality of digital interactions Human flourishing
	Moderations tools	Respect (rights) – being treated as a morally responsible agent	
	Algorithms	Esteem (social value) – having one’s contributions valued	

Social media bans represent a withdrawal from technology. The premise is a withdrawal from (negative) recognition. However, bans:

- can signal exclusion from a community (loss of belonging)
- may deny one’s voice or legitimacy (loss of respect)
- can devalue one’s participation (loss of social esteem)

Foregrounding digital engagement through a lens of positive, intersubjective recognition enables a more developmental understanding of youth wellbeing, one that aims to give digital users agency and supports sustained, long-term outcomes rather than short-term behavioural control.

Conclusion

While social media bans may reduce social media use and increase engagement in offline activities such as sports, reading, and family time, these reductions are currently still partial, given that circumvention of restrictions is still widespread, and long-term mental health benefits remain unverified.

Our work with young people focused on their digital experiences indicates that social media bans risk obscuring the structural sources of harm. Online risks are shaped primarily by platform design, commercial incentives, and insufficient regulatory power, rather than by youth participation alone.

These discussions present an opportunity to refocus policy on:

- Proportionate and effective regulation through international collaboration and engagement with jurisdictions holding significant regulatory influence, particularly the United States, to ensure the effective enforcement of standards and sanctions
- Corporate accountability
- Rights-based, empowerment-focused pedagogical approaches
- Shared societal responsibility
- A broader understanding of wellbeing as contingent on positive, intersubjective experiences online
- Expansion of safe, structured opportunities for youth engagement in offline settings

References:

- Costa, C. (2026). *Digital Influences and conceptions of masculinity: Rethinking wellbeing through a lens of interpersonal recognition*. Durham University.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19499566>
- Costa, C., & Oliver, M. (2023). *The Durham Digital Literacy Project*. Durham University.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16790.93768>
- Costa, C., & Oliver, M. (2025a). Young people and digital literacy learning: Co-producing critical citizenship practices. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 0(0), 1–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2025.2593611>
- Costa, C., & Oliver, M. (2025b). *Digital Literacies with and for young people Co-producing picture books to promote digital cultural knowledge*. Durham University
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15063.38569>
- Costa, C., Oliver, M., & Oliver, P. (2026). *Rethinking digital wellbeing through a perspective of intersubjective recognition*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19205844>
- Bursztyjn, L., Duckworth, A. L., Jiménez-Durán, R., Leonard, A., Milojević, F., Roth, C., & Sunstein, C. R. (2026). *Why Bans Fail: Tipping Points and Australia's Social Media Ban* (Working Paper No. 35162). National Bureau of Economic Research.
<https://doi.org/10.3386/w35162>

- Ceilutka, K. (2023). The discontents of competition for recognition on social media: Perfectionism, resentment, and collective narcissism. *Philosophy & Social Criticism*, 49(4), 409–430. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01914537211072883>
- Irani, F., Muotka, J., Lyyra, P., Parviainen, T., & Monto, S. (2024). Social influence in adolescence: Behavioral and neural responses to peer and expert opinion. *Social Neuroscience*, 19(1), 25–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17470919.2024.2323745>
- Internet Matters.org. (2026). *The Online Safety Act: Are children safer online?* <https://www.internetmatters.org/hub/research/online-safety-act-report-2026/>
- Laursen, B., & Veenstra, R. (2021). Toward understanding the functions of peer influence: A summary and synthesis of recent empirical research. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 31(4), 889–907. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12606>
- Mou, Y., Wu, K., & Atkin, D. (2016). Understanding the use of circumvention tools to bypass online censorship. *New Media & Society*, 18(5), 837–856. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444814548994>
- Notley, T., Chambers, S., Dezuanni, M., Park, S., & Lee, J. Y. (2026). *Social media ban: The impact on young people's news engagement*. (Australia). <https://apo.org.au/node/334363>
- ofcom. (2024). *A third of children have false social media age of 18+*. [Www.Ofcom.Org.Uk. https://www.ofcom.org.uk/online-safety/protecting-children/a-third-of-children-have-false-social-media-age-of-18](https://www.ofcom.org.uk/online-safety/protecting-children/a-third-of-children-have-false-social-media-age-of-18)
- Srivastava, S. (2026). Platform rule: Facebook, corporate power, and networked publics. *European Journal of International Relations*, 13540661261444845. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13540661261444845>

Appendix 1:

Social media bans **A shared perspective from members of the Durham Youth Council**

Coordinated and written up by Dr Cristina Costa at Durham University, with the support of Ms Cat Harwood

1. Age of responsibility

Through the youth debate held in Durham, alongside focus groups and a co-production workshop, young people initially tended to place responsibility for digital safety and wellbeing on adults. This was evident in discussions advocating for restrictions as well as those supporting digital freedoms.

Some participants proposed setting the age of restriction at 11, aligning more closely with the current age of digital consent. They argued that at this stage, primary schools are often better positioned to support children's social development and help bridge connection gaps. They also suggested that, at this age, the potential harms of digital engagement may outweigh the benefits.

Participants suggested that such a restriction could "incentivise children to spend more time outdoors or with friends, reducing screen time and reliance on digital devices for entertainment". They also felt that setting the threshold at a younger, more manageable age might encourage parents to take greater responsibility in limiting social media use, as it would seem more achievable than stricter age limits currently being discussed. They also agreed that ensuring accountability in digital engagement requires a multifaceted approach.

2. Accountability, regulation, and transparency

Technology companies should be held accountable for their platforms in the same way as any other product placed on the market. When products are harmful or unsafe for consumers, they are recalled; similar principles should apply to digital platforms. This requires stronger regulation of algorithms and platform design, particularly where there is evidence of harm.

The role of the state should focus on regulation rather than control of users. Government oversight should prioritise users' rights and technology companies' responsibilities, especially regarding the impact of digital platforms on mental health. Because mental health harms are less visible than physical harms, stronger and more proactive safeguards are needed.

Financial penalties alone are unlikely to ensure compliance from technology companies. Where companies fail to meet regulatory standards, stronger measures should be considered, including banning their platforms within the country. Revenue generated

from sanctions should be directed toward supporting the individuals and groups affected.

Governments also require greater insight into how technology companies operate. Increased transparency around data use, algorithmic decision-making, and platform governance is essential.

3. Responsibility

Current proposals to ban social media tend to position children as the primary bearers of responsibility for online harms. This framing is flawed. Responsibility should be shared, but distributed in proportion to each actor's power, influence, and role in shaping digital environments.

A more accurate way to conceptualise this is through an inverted pyramid of responsibility, where accountability increases with structural control and decision-making power:

Figure 1 – Inverted pyramid of responsibility

- **Government** sits at the top, with primary responsibility for regulation, accountability, transparency, and enforcement of standards that protect users' rights and wellbeing.
- **Technology companies** follow very closely, as the designers, owners, and profiteers of digital platforms. They shape online experiences through

commercial models, algorithms, and design choices and therefore carry substantial responsibility for harm and safety.

- **Parents and responsible adults** play an important supportive role, offering guidance, mediation, and care, but operate within environments they did not design or control.
- **Children and young people** sit at the base of the pyramid. They should be recognised as rights-holders with agency and responsibilities, but not burdened with accountability for systemic harms created by others.

This model challenges child-centric blame and re-centres responsibility on those with the greatest capacity to prevent harm. Positioning children at the base recognises their limited power while affirming their right to participation and expression.

4. The issue with blanket social media bans

Blanket bans lack a context-sensitive approach and disproportionately affect certain groups. Home-schooled children, for example, often rely on online spaces to maintain friendships, communicate, access peer learning, pursue hobbies, and find communities of shared interest. Removing these spaces risks increased isolation.

Bans also overlook the social consequences of exclusion. Young people with mixed-age friendship groups may be cut off from shared conversations and experiences, leading to social marginalisation.

Moreover, bans fail to recognise the forms of expression and belonging that social media enables, particularly for young people who feel marginalised or excluded in face to face settings. Many find reassurance, understanding, and a sense of belonging online.

5. The paradoxes in social media bans proposals

There are notable inconsistencies in proposals to ban social media. Gaming platforms often include social networking features, but are not subject to the same scrutiny. Educational and communication tools such as Microsoft Teams have also been reported as sites of harassment, yet are excluded from bans. Similarly, Gen-AI tools, some of which are used as substitutes for counselling or therapy with drastic consequences, are rarely discussed, despite posing significant risks to young people.

These bans create a paradox: they stimulate debate about wellbeing and safety, yet they do not address the underlying issues in a developmental or supportive way. Instead, they imply that once a young person reaches 16, they can suddenly use social media responsibly without any preparation, education, or support systems in place.

Additionally, if digital inclusion and the development of digital literacies are stated government priorities, also reflected in the expanding use of digital technologies across educational settings, it is unclear how these objectives can be realised if young people are expected to withdraw from online environments. Digital literacy extends beyond the

acquisition of technical competencies; it encompasses the capacity to navigate digital spaces critically, safely, and ethically, and to participate responsibly in digital spaces. Limiting young people's access to these environments risks undermining efforts to cultivate the very skills, understanding, and ethical engagement that current education and inclusion strategies seek to promote.

6. Misplaced liability

From a young person's perspective, social media bans move the liability of social media issues onto users rather than addressing systemic problems. This can give the impression that the government does not fully understand how social media works and is avoiding more complex discussions regarding the root causes of harm.

Tech companies design platforms that can create, exploit, and exacerbate mental health problems. Framing the issue as a "child problem" rather than a technical and commercial one redirects responsibility to those who have very little say on how these platforms are created and managed. The fundamental question remains: is this primarily a social issue or a technical one?

7. Educational opportunities for everyone

This debate creates an educational opportunity for everyone. Education should not be limited to young people. Parents and the wider public also need support to understand digital environments, as adults are equally affected by online harms. No one is immune to the influence of social media.

There is also a broader need for public understanding of the power of Tech Companies. These platforms can shape trends, ideologies, movements, and public discourse. They can technically privilege certain voices over others, and history shows that dominant Tech Companies have exercised such power. This reinforces that the issue is technical and structural, not individual.

8. The commercialisation and quality of digital engagement

A major concern not addressed by blanket social media bans is the implicit commercial nature of social media and its impact on digital experience. This includes:

- Exposure to digital influencers promoting unrealistic lifestyles, wealth, and consumption
- Algorithmic amplification that prioritises engagement over wellbeing
- Tolerance of toxic behaviours
- Censorship or suppression of counter-narratives

These features and the engineering of digital environments shape how young people experience digital spaces and can contribute significantly to harm.

9. Why social media is difficult to give up: a youth perspective

Social media plays many positive roles in young people's lives, including:

- Maintaining contact with friends

- Participating in mixed-age social groups
- Accessing diverse perspectives, increasing social and political awareness (when paired with the ability to fact-check)
- Learning about global movements, cultures, and social issues
- Exposure to positive stories, activism, and healthy debate
- Accessing informal learning opportunities that expand horizons
- Exploring interests and skills without fear or embarrassment “of not knowing how” (e.g. cooking, crafts, sports, art)

There is no singular narrative of harm; the reality is complex and multifaceted.

10. Ideal social media designs

Ideally, digital environments prioritise wellbeing over profit. Key features should include:

- Media not driven by advertising or commercial interests
- Strong regulation of digital influencers, including bans on irresponsible promotion and false advertising
- Measures to limit over-consumerism
- Removal or limitations of direct messaging
- Algorithms that avoid echo chambers, ideological filtering, and programmed censorship
- A revival of responsible journalism, including ethical citizen journalism
- Transparent information practices serving the public interest rather than corporate ideology

11. Supporting young people as ethical digital agents

Rather than banning access, young people’s responsibilities should be foregrounded through a co-created code of conduct that recognises them as ethical participants in digital life. This could include commitments to:

- Use respectful language, agreed contextually
- Avoid intentionally hurting others, regardless of popularity or “likes”
- Reject any form of hate content (e.g.: based on beliefs, race, religion, etc.)
- Report harmful content, even when not personally targeted
- Avoid raising sensitive issues publicly unless relevant to the topic
- Act honestly and truthfully, with stricter standards for content creators
- Avoid false advertising or self-profit at others’ expense
- Support others rather than undermine them
- Hold digital influencers accountable for toxic or misleading content, including both overtly negative and unrealistically “perfect” portrayals of life
- Distinguish clearly between public and private information, recognising the potential harm of oversharing